

Impregnation Performance of Non-Isobaric Processes

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ABSTRACT

Fiber Reinforced Thermoplastic Polymer Composites (FRTPC) offer a great weight saving potential and the opportunity for large scale production with short cycle times. Therefore, FRTPCs became increasingly popular in the recent years. In order to improve the production process of these materials, this article presents a process model, which is capable to predict the impregnation performance for non-isobaric process conditions. At first, a detailed case study for different temperature and pressure settings with regard to the impregnation performance is shown. This examination revealed that there is a logarithmic correlation between the permeability of the textile and the applied pressure. Thus, the efficiency of the process is lower at higher process pressure. In addition it will be shown that the permeability values are not affected by the process temperature. Based on these results the advancement of the so called B-Factor model was carried out for non-isobaric process conditions. With the help of the modified model, different process conditions become comparable to each other and the impregnation performance can be rated. Finally, the article shows the validation of the non-isobaric B-Factor model by means of samples produced under different process conditions and offering the same impregnation quality.

1 INTRODUCTION

Due to their specific properties such as high toughness or excellent fatigue performance, the demand for fiber reinforced thermoplastic composites has steadily increased. These materials are used for many applications in different industries, e.g. as sole or ski reinforcements in sport industry, as bumper beams in the automotive industry or leading edges in aeronautic industry. Thereby, thermoplastic composites offer the advantage of short cycle times of the forming process due to the use of semi-finished products, so called organic sheets [1]. But in order to promote the penetration of the market, all steps of the production process have to be advanced. One important aspect is the modelling of the production and impregnation process, because there is presently no meaningful alternative, which considers the material and process properties correctly. The most relevant restrictions are the pressure dependency of the textile compaction and the permeability. These aspects are of major interest, because nearly every production method offers a inhomogeneous pressure distribution inside the tool. Scope of the paper is to introduce a process model, which is capable to predict the impregnation performance for non-isobaric process conditions.

2 MODELLING OF THE THERMOPLASTIC IMPREGNATION PROCESS

2.1 Basic process model

In the recent years, numerous approaches have been developed to describe the impregnation process of thermoplastic fiber reinforced materials. Due to the large number of associated factors influencing the real process, the reduction of complexity is necessary [2]. Thus, the developed models focus only on some aspects, or they can be adapted to real measurements by parameterization (e.g. calculation of permeability according to Carman-Kozeny or Papathanasiou [3, 4]). For the description of non-isobaric process conditions within the presented research work, a process model developed by Mayer [2] has been selected, which was originally developed for the organic sheet production using a isobaric double belt press [2]. The main advantage of this model is that all effects occurring during the impregnation are considered implicitly. The basis is the so called b-Integral, which subsumes all factors influencing the impregnation process [2]. Regarding the process parameter the process speed and the temperature respectively the matrix viscosity are considered. Furthermore, more complex aspects like the relaxation behavior of the textile or the pressure and viscosity dependent flow front of the polymer are taken into account [2]. The b-Integral is given in Equation 1.

$$b = \int_{t_0(T_m)}^{t_n(T_c)} \frac{l}{\eta_0(T(t))} dt \quad (1)$$

The integration of the reciprocal viscosity as a function of the time is carried out within the limits t_0 and t_n (Figure 1). These limits are defined by reaching the melting temperature T_m and the recrystallization temperature T_c [2]. If the process temperature profile cannot be predicted by a model, the calculation can also be done as a sum of reciprocal viscosity points for individual temperature steps (see Equation 2) [2]:

$$b = \sum_{k=0}^n t_k \cdot \frac{l}{\eta_0(T_k)} \quad (2)$$

In order to define the b-Integral representing the process parameters, which are leading to a fully impregnated FRPC for the specific material set-up, the associated process conditions have to be identified experimentally. Then, the b-Integral is calculated afterwards. Figure 1 illustrates the calculation exemplarily for a temperature dependent viscosity curve.

Temperature dependent matrix viscosity

b-integral calculation

Figure 1: Calculation of the b-Integral.

Once, the b-Integral is determined, it can represent different process conditions, i.e. the same b-Integral can reflect different combinations of process temperature and process speeds respectively duration time. Thus, on the one hand it becomes possible to define alternative process parameters, which are also leading to a fully impregnated FRPC. On the other hand, different processes can be

compared to each other. But in addition to the parameters temperature and time, the real impregnation process is also determined by the process pressure. In order to consider this parameter, the so called B-factor is defined. Therefore, the b-Integral is multiplied with the applied pressure P (see equation 3).

$$B = b \cdot P \quad (3)$$

Thus, the impregnation performance is characterized by the B-factor with regard to temperature, pressure and time for a specific material set-up. However, the validity of this impregnation model requires isobaric process conditions with a homogeneous pressure distribution inside the tool.

2.2 Restrictions of the process model

In order to define the limitations of the B-factor model, the mathematical and physical correlations will be analyzed in this chapter. As shown in chapter 2.1, the calculation of the b-factor is not linked to aspects determining the impregnation speed e.g. permeability of the reinforcement (see Equation 3). If different processes should be evaluated it becomes necessary that the impregnation proceeds comparable in both processes [2]. The requirement of having a stacking of fabric and polymer as also focusing on the impregnation procedure is fulfilled if the overall reduction of thickness as a function of the B-factor is identical. (Figure 2). The thickness reduction can be described with a spring-buffer model according to Kelvin-Voigt and is characterized by three phases (see Figure 2):

- I. Thickness reduction due to an elastic compression of the reinforcement
- II. Thickness reduction due to impregnation of macro porosities
- III. Thickness reduction due to impregnation of micro porosities

Each phase is separated by the corresponding laminate thickness and the B-factor values reached at this point. H_0 is the starting point of the impregnation process, H' (dH_z / dB) is the actual thickness during the process and H_a represents the thickness of a fully impregnated laminate. For the model it is assumed, that the final thickness of a specific fully impregnated laminate is always the same for a specific material set-up. It doesn't matter, which process or process parameters have been used to get the fully impregnated laminate.

Figure 2: Characterization of the impregnation and consolidation behavior by means of the laminate thickness reduction.

The mathematical formulation of this curve is given in Equation 4. It can be seen, that the thickness reduction as a function of time $\varepsilon(t)$ depends on the acting force σ , the spring constant E of the fabric stack and the specific damping d of fabric, and matrix (see Equation 4).

$$\varepsilon(t) = \frac{\sigma}{E} \cdot \left[1 - \exp\left(-\frac{E}{d} \cdot t\right) \right] \quad (4)$$

Due to different mathematical and physical aspects, this formulation can be simplified. First of all, only the progression of the thickness reduction is relevant for the model. This is leading to the formulation given in Equation 5:

$$\varepsilon(t) = \frac{\sigma}{E} \cdot \left[1 - \exp\left(-\frac{E}{d} \cdot t\right) \right] \triangleq \frac{\sigma}{E} \cdot \exp\left(-\frac{E}{d} \cdot t\right) \quad (5)$$

Furthermore, the thickness reduction as a function of time can be interpreted as expansion between the initial and the final thickness. The laminate thickness at a specific time is H_i and the thickness reduction can be calculated as $\varepsilon = (H_a - H_i)/H_a$, which leads to Equation 6:

$$H_a - H_i = H_a \cdot \frac{\sigma}{E} \cdot \exp\left(-\frac{E}{d} \cdot t\right) \quad (6)$$

Taken into account, that $H_a \cdot \frac{\sigma}{E}$ represents the starting point H_{\max} of the curve, which is the initial thickness of the laminate, this leads to:

$$H_a - H_i = H_{\max} \cdot \exp\left(-\frac{E}{d} \cdot t\right) \quad (7)$$

Applying this equation to the real impregnation process, the time dependent compression $\frac{E}{d}$ represents a compression rate and can be seen as an equivalent to the polymer flow during the impregnation process.

The thickness reduction during the impregnation can also be linked to D'Arcys Law which is commonly used to describe the flow behavior of liquids in porous materials. The first part of equation 8 describes the impregnation progress ($H_a - H_i$) depending on the reinforcement, permeability K , matrix viscosity and impregnation pressure while the second part of Equation 8 shows the relation of thickness reduction and B-factor model.

$$H_a - H_i \triangleq h^2 = -2K \cdot \frac{t \cdot \Delta P}{\eta} = -2K \cdot \frac{t}{\eta} \cdot \Delta P = -2K \cdot B \quad (8)$$

Having a look at Equation 8 it becomes obvious, that the impregnation progress ($H_a - H_i$) is determined by the porosity of the material K (\approx permeability) and the B-factor, which characterizes the impregnation performance with regard to pressure P , temperature ($=$ polymer viscosity η), and duration of the process t . But there are some differences between the restrictions of D'Arcys Law and the real impregnation process. The most relevant aspects are given in Table 1.

D'Arcys Law		Thermoplastic impregnation process
Polymer flow through	\leftrightarrow	Polymer saturation
Constant permeability	\leftrightarrow	Variable permeability
Constant viscosity	\leftrightarrow	Temperature dependent viscosity

Table 1: Major differences between D'Arcys Law and a real thermoplastic impregnation process.

Due to these differences, the parameter K representing the permeability of the textile for continuous flow has to be replaced by a new parameter k_s , which characterizes the saturation rate of a textile. A combination of the interpretation of Equation 7 with Equation 8 and the new parameter k_s results in Equation 9.

$$\frac{E}{d} \cdot t = 2K \cdot B = k_s \cdot B \quad (9)$$

Following this the reduction of thickness during the thermoplastic impregnation process can be described by the following Equation 10.

$$H_i - H_a = H_{\max} \cdot \exp(-k_S \cdot B) = H_{\max} \cdot \exp\left(-\frac{k_S \cdot P}{\eta} \cdot t\right) \quad (10)$$

In order to fulfill the requirements of the original B-factor model, the thickness reduction of the laminate during the impregnation process as a function of the b-factor has always to be the same, if different process conditions should be compared to each other. But when analyzing Equation 10, it becomes obvious, that this is only possible, if changes of k_S and B compensate each other. Alternatively, the material parameters have to be influenced by the process in the same way. In conclusion, it can be said, that the original B-factor model cannot be applied to processes with non-isobaric pressure conditions due to the explained restrictions.

3 EXPERIMENTAL EVALUATION

3.1 Materials in use

For the experimental evaluation of the impregnation process, a glass fiber textile of Hexcel (type 1038; 2/2 twill weave; area weight: 600 g/m²) has been selected as reinforcement material and a standard polypropylene of Borealis (type bj100hp) has been chosen as matrix material (melting temperature: 164 °C). Due to the use of polypropylene in form of films with a thickness of 300 µm, a symmetric laminate lay-up of 4 layers textile (T), and 4 layers polymer films (P) has been realized. This is theoretically leading to a fiber volume content of 44 % and a thickness of 2.14 mm for a fully impregnated laminate.

In order to get the required rheological data for the calculation of the B-factor values, the polymer has been analyzed with a plate-plate-rheometer for five different temperatures in the range of 170 °C to 210 °C. Afterwards, the measurements have been approximated with the Arrhenius equation for any temperature in the molten state [5]. The results of the rheological analysis are given in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Rheological properties of the used polypropylene

3.2 Machinery equipment and sample preparation

The sample preparation using different temperature and pressure settings has been carried out with a small static press, which enables very high heating and cooling rates. Some more details about the press are given in Table 2.

Parameter		Range of values
Temperature	[°C]	20 - 500
Heating rate	[K/s]	0 - 10
Cooling rate	[K/s]	0 - 5
Pressing area	[mm ²]	58 x 58
Pressing force	[kN]	0 - 5

Table 2: Technical details of the used static press.

For the sample preparation, a circular tool with a diameter of 50 mm has been used (see Figure 4). In order to avoid any influence of different heating/cooling rates on the impregnation process, the laminate set-up has been placed inside the cold tool and for each cycle, a controlled heating rate of 1 K/s and a cooling rate of 0,5 K/s has been defined. As process parameters, four different temperature settings have been selected (180 °C, 190 °C, 200 °C and 210 °C). For each setting, the process duration has been set to 2,000 seconds, which was long enough to guarantee fully impregnated samples. Because only the impregnation process was studied within this research work, long holding time after full impregnation doesn't affect the evaluation with the B-factor model. For each temperature setting five samples have been produced using a different pressure setting for each (5 bar, 10 bar, 15 bar, 20 bar and 25 bar).

The thickness reduction of the laminate during the sample preparation has been recorded with a video camera. Therefore, at the outside of the tool has been marked with a white line in order to enable a good visual evaluation quality via pixel tracking (see figure 4). The impregnation progress (tool movement) has been analyzed with the Software Motion Studio (producer: IDT Inc.) by means of the movement of these pixels offering a high contrast.

Figure 4: Circular tool used for the sample preparation

Figure 5 shows the thickness reduction during the impregnation process exemplarily. In conformity with the state-of-art, in the first step the reinforcing material is compacted. Afterwards, the macro- and micro-impregnation takes place. Due to the big differences in void size, the micro-impregnation is characterized by a significant lower thickness reduction rate. But having a look at the end of the process (see also detail section in Figure 5) it seems, as if no limit value in thickness is reached, although the samples are fully impregnated. As reason for this effect, the polymer squeeze out of the tools shearing edges has been identified. Since it is of major importance for the application of the B-factor model, that the real thickness reduction is evaluated, the polymer squeeze out of the tool has been considered. Therefore, the amount of polymer has been recorded for each sample and the

thickness reduction has been adjusted afterwards. Finally, a constant thickness of each sample at the end of the impregnation process was reached (for more details see [6]).

Figure 5: Thickness reduction of the laminate due to the impregnation process

3.3 Analysis of the impregnation process

The evaluation of the impregnation process for different temperature and pressure settings by means of the thickness reduction was carried out using the B-factor model as a sum of individual values (see Equation 2). Therefore, the required viscosity values of the matrix material have been calculated using the temperature profile recorded by the static press and the Arrhenius equation (see Figure 3). The pressure has been supposed to be constant during the process for each parameter setting. Due to the use of a comparatively small tool, this seems to be approvable. Furthermore, the cooling cycle has not been taken into account, because the shrinkage cannot be considered by the spring-buffer model according to Kelvin-Voigt. The results of the evaluation are shown in Figure 6 and Figure 7 for all parameter settings.

Figure 6: Thickness reduction of the laminate for different process parameters (part I)

Figure 7: Thickness reduction of the laminate for different process parameters (part II)

The diagrams clearly show that the thickness of the samples converges to the same values for all parameter settings, i.e. full impregnation is reached for each sample. But on the other side it becomes obvious, that the thickness reduction as a function of the B-factor is different for all settings. Because of this, it is not possible to compare the impregnations performance of processes operating at different pressure values by means of the original B-factor model.

In order to evaluate the impregnation process in more detail, the mathematical function according to Equation 10 has been adapted to every parameter setting in a next step. Therefore, the saturation rate k_s has been fitted to the real measurements. The resulting k_s values are shown in Figure 8.

Figure 8: Saturation rate k_s for different temperature and pressure settings determined by the real thickness reduction

Because of the individual thickness reduction function, there are different values for the saturation rate k_s for all parameter settings. However, Figure 8 shows that the values are similar for different process temperatures, but there is a big variety for different pressures. Consequently it is proved, that the permeability during the saturation of the textile is affected by the pressure, which is not considered

of the original B-factor model. Nevertheless, the influence of the temperature on the impregnation performance is considered correctly by the model.

4 ADVANCEMENT OF THE PROCESS MODEL

Based on the experimental evaluation of the impregnation process shown in chapter 3, the advancement of the B-factor model has been carried out. Initial point was Equation 10, which can be rewritten as follows:

$$\Delta H = H_{\max} \cdot \exp(-k_S(P) \cdot B) \quad (11)$$

It is assumed, that the total thickness reduction during the impregnation process is always the same for a defined material set-up and it is not affected by the process parameters, in particular the applied pressure. Thus, the following transformations can be done:

$$\Delta H_{P_1} = \Delta H_{P_2} \quad (12)$$

$$\Leftrightarrow H_{\max} \cdot \exp(-k_S(P_1) \cdot b \cdot P_1) = H_{\max} \cdot \exp(-k_S(P_2) \cdot b \cdot P_2) \quad (13)$$

$$\Leftrightarrow -k_S(P_1) \cdot P_1 = -k_S(P_2) \cdot P_2 \quad (14)$$

$$\Leftrightarrow P_1 = \frac{k_S(P_2)}{k_S(P_1)} \cdot P_2 \quad (15)$$

If the specific saturation rate k_S has been determined once, different process pressures can be converted into each other on the basis of Equation 15. As a consequence, it becomes possible to compare different process configurations to each other with regard to their impregnation performance. Furthermore, the impregnation performance of any process offering arbitrary inhomogeneous pressure and temperature profiles can be characterized. Therefore, a virtual isobaric reference pressure is defined and the modified B-factor is calculated according to Equation 16 for continuous values and Equation 17 for discrete values.

$$B = \int_{t_0(T_m)}^{t_n(T_c)} \frac{I}{\eta_0(T(t))} \cdot \frac{k(P_{Ref})}{k(P(t))} \cdot P_{Ref} \cdot dt \quad (16)$$

$$B = \sum_{k=0}^n \left[t_k \cdot \frac{I}{\eta_0(T_k)} \cdot \frac{k(P_{Ref})}{k(P(t_k))} \cdot P_{Ref} \right] \quad (17)$$

Despite the shown modification, it is not possible to transfer process parameter to another machine, if there are big differences between the impregnation processes. Effects, which are not considered by the modified model are e.g. the options for air displacement (determined by tool size or design of shearing edges) or the polymer flow during the impregnation (in plane vs. orthogonal polymer flow).

For the validation of the modified model, two samples have been processed and the impregnation quality has been compared to each other. Because the modifications are only affecting the pressure, the same temperature, but a different pressure, should be used. A temperature of 210 °C and a pressure of 5 bar and 25 bar has been selected. The processing time can be defined with the help of the data generated during the experimental evaluation (see chapter 3). B-factor values representing a complete impregnation for 210 °C at 5 bar and at 25 bar are 17 and 87 respectively gathered from the experimental data (see Figure 9). It's important to point out, that both values are representing the same impregnation quality, although they are very different.

Figure 9: Determination of B-factor values enabling full impregnation by means of the thickness reduction

Because the same material set-up and the same machinery equipment are used for both samples, the gathered B-factor values have to fulfill equation 15 when using the corresponding saturation rates (see Figure 8). The calculation is given below:

$$P_1 = \frac{k_s(P_2)}{k_s(P_1)} \cdot P_2 \Rightarrow 5\text{bar} \approx \frac{0,108}{0,558} \cdot 25\text{bar} \quad (18)$$

In order to predict the process time necessary to fulfill the two B-factor values, two steps have been carried out. In the first step, the B-factor values portion for the heating and cooling cycle has been calculated with the help of Equation 17 according to the performance of the pressing equipment (B_{heating} and B_{cooling}). Afterwards, the process part offering constant temperature in between heating and cooling has been calculated considering the limitation by the residual B-factor (see Equation 19).

$$B_{\text{const}} = B - (B_{\text{heating}} + B_{\text{cooling}}) \quad (18)$$

The result of this calculation is given in Figure 10. The two process cycles show clearly, that the total process time to reach the target B-factor is nearly the same, although there is a huge difference in pressure (5 bar vs. 25 bar). Once again, this makes clear that the pressure does not affect the impregnation performance linearly.

To verify the assumption, that the target B-factor is reached, the impregnation quality was evaluated by micrographs of polished cross sections (see Figure 10). The pictures clearly show that there is no difference in impregnation quality between both samples. Hence, the defined process parameters, deduced from the experimentally determined B-factor values, are both leading to a fully impregnated laminate. Consequently, the modified B-factor model is suitable for the evaluation and comparison of processes offering non-isobaric process condition.

Figure 10: Comparison of impregnation quality for different process parameters

4 CONCLUSION

Organic sheets offer a great market potential due to their excellent properties and their capability for large scale production. But for further penetration of the market, process simulation is of major importance in order to increase quality and reduce price of organic sheets. Because of this, within the research work presented in this paper, important basic findings have been made. Based on the B-factor model and an experimental evaluation, it was shown, that the permeability of a reinforcing textile is significantly affected by the applied process pressure. The higher the applied pressure, the lower is the permeability and the more inefficient is the impregnation process. This effect was not considered of the original B-factor model. In order to modify the model, the permeability for saturation has been defined, which is determined by the thickness reduction of the laminate during the impregnation process. It was found, that the permeability of saturation is only affected by the process pressure and not by the temperature. Based on this correlation, the modification of the B-factor model has been carried out, which makes the model suitable for the evaluation and comparison of processes offering non-isobaric condition. Thus, with the help of the modified B-factor model, the prediction quality for real production processes is significantly improved. This allows to improve quality and reduce price of organic sheets.

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